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THE IMPACT OF SOIL CULTIVATION, IRRIGATION METHODS, AND FERTILIZER RATES ON THE GROWTH AND BRANCHING OF THE SOYBEAN VARIETY SIGALIA

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Abstract

Global ecological processes in nature require the development of new soil cultivation technologies and fertilization systems that save energy resources for various agro-ecological regions and crops. Increasing the yield of leguminous crops is one of the pressing issues in modern agricultural science.

Keywords: soil cultivation, plowing depth, soybean, growth, branching, fertilization, irrigation

The Ganja-Dashkasan region holds significant importance in the agricultural production of our republic. Therefore, considering the above, it is crucial to conserve energy resources while maintaining soil fertility, especially given the high costs of fuel and lubricants in a market economy. Enhancing the productivity and quality of soybeans as a food, feed, and industrial crop in the region is a relevant problem. This involves studying the efficiency of soil cultivation and mineral fertilizers in stubble fields, i.e., after barley harvest.

Soybeans are sensitive to fertilization. Experiments have shown that to produce 20 quintals of soybean seeds, 142 kg of N, 32 kg of P₂O₅, and 35 kg of K₂O are needed. Under primary plowing, 60-90 kg of N, 60-90 kg of P₂O₅, and 30-54 kg of K₂O should be applied. 30% of nitrogen fertilizer should be applied before sowing, the rest as top dressing in two stages: 40% 2-3 weeks after emergence and 30% during pod formation and seed filling. Fertilizers can be applied using RUM-5.1 and RMQ-4 fertilizer spreaders.

First-class seeds should be used for sowing. Seeds should be treated with rhizotorphin at 200 grams per hectare before sowing. This amount of rhizotorphin is dissolved in 1.2 liters of water and sprayed on the seeds. To combat diseases like bacteriosis, root rot, aminomycosis, and fusariosis, seeds should be treated with 1-2 kg of 70% taciqrان per ton 3-4 weeks before sowing. Applying 20-25 tons of manure per hectare under autumn plowing yields good results. Timely and quality fertilization significantly enhances soybean yields. An additional 50-60 kg of nitrogen fertilizer per hectare should be applied in two stages. In autumn sowing, after seedlings emerge, 180 kg of superphosphate fertilizer should be applied. Microorganisms, especially molybdenum, boron, manganese, and others, play a significant role in increasing soybean productivity. Mineral fertilizers treated with these microelements should be used [2, p.120-122].

Soybeans need significant amounts of phosphorus and potassium fertilizers. Applying 180-200 kg of superphosphate and 1 quintal of potassium fertilizer under primary plowing yields positive results. During

sowing, 20-30 kg of P₂O₅ should be applied in rows. In less fertile soils, using microelements is advisable.

Increasing soybean cultivation in Azerbaijan could reduce imports of certain product groups. Soybeans are known for being rich in oil (18-24%), protein (40%), carbohydrates (30%), mineral substances (5%), and numerous vitamins and proteins. 50% of the world's vegetable oils come from soybeans. Soy is used both as human food and animal feed. Due to its high protein content, soybean feed is highly beneficial for livestock. 70% of the world's feed consumption is soybean-based. Adding soybean flour to livestock diets increases their mass by 30%, milk production by 25%, and adding 10 grams to poultry feed increases their mass by 39% and egg production by 20%. Soybeans are also beneficial in agriculture, as they transfer nitrogen from the atmosphere to the soil, increasing the yield of subsequent crops. Additionally, soy is widely used in industry for products like flour, milk, yogurt, and cheese, as well as paint, canvas, and adhesives [3, p.215-220].

Soybeans are the most widely grown leguminous crop worldwide and are considered the primary plant for protein production. Currently, soybean production is ensured by expanding cultivation areas. Authors believe developing various cultivation technologies to increase soybean productivity is crucial [4, p.64-68].

Due to its high protein and oil content, soybeans are essential for human, animal, and poultry nutrition. Rich in amino acids, soybeans are a vital protein source comparable to meat products [6, p.163-165].

A directive from the Russian president aims to increase soybean oil production and exports by 2025 by efficiently using land resources, changing the structure of cultivated areas, and developing effective and innovative scientific research. Expanding cultivation areas in traditional soybean-growing regions and introducing soybean cultivation in other regions are deemed necessary.

L.A. Svetashov, E.V. Klimkin, and A.F. Klimkin note that the demand for vegetable oils, including unique soybean oil, has recently increased. Efficient cultivation technologies are essential for soybean

productivity, as with other agricultural crops [7, p.190-196].

Soybeans (*Glycine max* L.) are annual herbaceous plants belonging to the Fabaceae family. Soy products have been used since 3000 BC. Soy products, rich in proteins, vitamins B, iron, calcium, potassium, and essential fatty acids, are used in treating cardiovascular diseases and strengthening bones. Currently, soy is widely cultivated in Asian countries, the USA, Canada, and Western Europe [5, p.18-20].

In terms of cultivated area, soybeans rank first among leguminous crops, attributed to their unique biological and economic characteristics [8, p.21-24].

In Russia, K.A. Khamokov considers developing new energy-saving cultivation technologies for increasing soybean productivity crucial. He notes that soil cultivation is a fundamental factor in growing agricultural crops and that technological processes should be minimized.

Different opinions on soil cultivation are linked to its zonal characteristics. This means that any soil cultivation method should be chosen considering the specific agro-ecological conditions of the area. In modern agriculture, soil conservation and energy-saving approaches include: conventional plowing, deep plowing with or without soil layers, two-layer deep plowing, shallow cultivation, minimization, and zero (No-till) cultivation. These methods are effective when chosen correctly based on specific requirements. Soil-climatic conditions of the area, the biological characteristics of the cultivated crops, soil fertility indicators, and phytosanitary status should be considered. Direct sowing or zero (No-till) cultivation can be applied to soils with sufficient moisture in the arable layer, natural compaction close to optimal, and favorable phytosanitary conditions [1, p.7-10].

Thus, mineral fertilizers significantly affect the height of soybeans against the backdrop of soil cultivation after barley harvest on irrigated gray-brown (chest-

nut) soils. As shown in the table, the variant with plowing at a depth of 15-20 cm, pivot irrigation, and applying N80P60K40 per hectare resulted in plant heights of 21.3 cm during the branching phase, 42.4 cm during the flowering phase, and 71.6 cm during the seed maturation phase. With N100P80K50 per hectare, plant heights were 22.6 cm during the branching phase, 44.7 cm during the flowering phase, and 74.3 cm during the seed maturation phase.

In the variant with plowing at a depth of 15-20 cm, drip irrigation, and applying N80P60K40 per hectare, plant heights were 24.3 cm during the branching phase, 44.6 cm during the flowering phase, and 75.9 cm during the seed maturation phase. With N100P80K50 per hectare, plant heights were 26.8 cm during the branching phase, 46.8 cm during the flowering phase, and 78.5 cm during the seed maturation phase.

As seen from the table, the variant with plowing at a depth of 20-25 cm, pivot irrigation, and applying N80P60K40 per hectare resulted in plant heights of 23.4 cm during the branching phase, 44.6 cm during the flowering phase, and 74.5 cm during the seed maturation phase. With N100P80K50 per hectare, plant heights were 24.7 cm during the branching phase, 46.8 cm during the flowering phase, and 77.4 cm during the seed maturation phase.

In the variant with plowing at a depth of 20-25 cm, drip irrigation, and applying N80P60K40 per hectare, plant heights were 26.5 cm during the branching phase, 48.9 cm during the flowering phase, and 79.8 cm during the seed maturation phase. With N100P80K50 per hectare, plant heights were 26.9 cm during the branching phase, 49.8 cm during the flowering phase, and 80.6 cm during the seed maturation phase.

The table analysis shows that the variant with plowing at a depth of 20-25 cm, drip irrigation, and applying N80P60K40 per hectare had significantly higher plant heights during the branching phase compared to other variants. Overall, plant development was more active during the phases with drip irrigation.

Table 1

Effect of Soil Tillage, Irrigation Methods, and Fertilizer Norms on Soybean Height (cm)

Variants	Soil Tillage Depth (cm)	Irrigation Methods	Fertilizer Norms (kg/ha)	Branching	Flowering	Pod Maturation
	15-20 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	21.3	42.4	71.6
			N100P80K50	22.6	44.7	74.3
		Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	24.3	44.6	75.9
			N100P80K50	26.8	47.8	78.5
	20-25 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	23.4	44.6	74.5
			N100P80K50	24.7	46.8	77.4
		Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	26.5	48.9	79.8
			N100P80K50	26.9	49.8	80.6

As seen from the table, in the 15-20 cm soil tillage depth with pivot irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches during the maturation phase is 10.5. With the same soil tillage depth and pivot irrigation, but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches is

11.6. In the 15-20 cm soil tillage depth with drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches is 12.7. With the same soil tillage depth and drip irrigation but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches is 14.8.

In the 20-25 cm soil tillage depth with pivot irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches during the maturation phase is 12.4. With the same soil tillage depth and pivot irrigation, but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches is 14.5. In the 20-25 cm soil tillage depth with drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches is 17.5. With the same soil tillage depth and

drip irrigation but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches is 15.8.

Thus, in irrigated gray-brown (chestnut) soils, mineral fertilizers have a significant impact on soybean branching in the context of soil tillage practices. In all cases, the highest indicators were observed with the drip irrigation method and a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare.

Table 2

**Effect of Soil Tillage, Irrigation Methods, and Fertilizer Norms on Soybean Branching
(Number of Branches)**

Soil Tillage Depth (cm)	Irrigation Method	Fertilizer Norms (kg/ha)	Number of Branches at Pod Maturation
15-20 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	10.5
		N100P80K50	11.6
20-25 cm	Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	12.7
		N100P80K50	14.8
20-25 cm	Pivot Irrigation	N80P60K40	12.4
		N100P80K50	14.5
20-25 cm	Drip Irrigation	N80P60K40	17.5
		N100P80K50	15.8

Conclusion

In the variant with 20-25 cm soil tillage depth, using drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the plant height at the branching stage was 26.5 cm, at flowering stage 48.9 cm, and at pod maturation stage 79.8 cm. In the same soil tillage depth with drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the plant height at the branching stage was 26.9 cm, at flowering stage 49.8 cm, and at pod maturation stage 80.6 cm.

In the 20-25 cm soil tillage depth with pivot irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches at pod maturation was 12.4. With the same soil tillage depth and pivot irrigation, but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches was 14.5. In the 20-25 cm soil tillage depth with drip irrigation and a fertilizer norm of N80P60K40 per hectare, the number of branches was 17.5. With the same soil tillage depth and drip irrigation, but with a fertilizer norm of N100P80K50 per hectare, the number of branches was 15.8.

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